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LINGUISTIC AND CULTURAL ISSUES IN TRANSLATION

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Abstract: This thesis is about the text translation, focusing on the challenges faced by translators in conveying meaning and bridging linguistic and cultural gaps. It discusses various translation methods and techniques, such as literal translation, transference, naturalization, cultural and functional equivalents, as well as issues related to lexicon, morphology, syntax, and semantics. The significance

of cultural words in literary translation is highlighted, and previous research studies on linguistic and cultural challenges are referenced.

Key words: Translation, linguistic gap, transference, terminology, disparities, cultural word, expressions, different aspects, sentences, flexibility, adaptation, original text, source language, target language.

The translation of literary works serves the purpose of reaching readers who speak different languages from the original text. According to Newmark, translation aims to convey the intended meaning of a text in another language, although this is not always achieved. Translation not only involves transferring information but also facilitates cultural exchange. To ensure the successful conveyance of the original text's intent and purpose across languages, translation requires careful application of various methods and procedures. Translators play a vital role in bridging the cultural divide. They need to possess a high level of proficiency in both languages, along with a deep understanding of their usage. Translators with the ability to recreate artistic works and a sensitivity to literary language can offer more creative translations. Furthermore, suggests that although translation is a practical skill, it is fundamentally based on theoretical principles.

Translation methods can be categorized into two main approaches: those that prioritize the source language (SL) and those that prioritize the target language (TL). Under the SL-focused approach, we find methods such as word-for-word translation, literal translation, faithful translation, and semantic translation. These methods aim to maintain a close correspondence with the original text. On the other hand, the TL-focused approach includes methods like adaptation, free translation, idiomatic translation, and communicative translation. These methods prioritize conveying the meaning and impact of the text in the target language, often allowing for more flexibility and adaptation. Each method serves as a distinct approach to bridge the linguistic and cultural gaps between the source and target languages during the translation process.

There are various techniques and approaches used in the process of translation. These methods can be applied to different aspects of language and

sentences, or they can encompass the entire text. Let's take a look at some of these techniques:

Literal Translation: This approach involves translating words or phrases directly, without considering cultural or linguistic differences. It aims to maintain the original structure as closely as possible.

Transference: Transference involves retaining certain words or phrases from the source language in the translation. This technique is commonly used for proper names, technical terms, or expressions that have become widely known in the target language.

Cultural Equivalent: This technique seeks to find an equivalent expression or concept in the target language that carries the same cultural meaning as the source language. It ensures that cultural nuances are preserved in the translation.

Through-translation: This technique involves translating a phrase or expression word-for-word, but rearranging the order to conform to the syntax of the target language.

Recognized Translation: Recognized translation refers to using a well-known or established translation that has been widely accepted by the target audience. This technique ensures consistency and familiarity.

Translation Label: Translation labels involve using specific terminology or markers to indicate that a word or phrase has been translated in the text. This is commonly used in technical or specialized translations.⁴⁷

Furthermore, the act of translating from one language to another presents fascinating challenges to investigate due to the inherent disparities between the two languages and their respective cultural contexts. Within the realm of language-related obstacles, there exist various issues pertaining to lexicon and morphology, syntax, and semantics during the translation process.

In the field of translation, the notion of "cultural term" or "cultural word" holds significant importance, particularly in literary translation. Literary translation involves the bilingual reworking of a literary piece and entails a wide range of

⁴⁷ P. Newmark, *A Textbook of Translation*, London, Prentice-Hall International Ltd. 1988. 132-136 pp

techniques, encompassing the comparison of natural language to knowledge processing. When it comes to cultural challenges, translators often categorize cultural words across various domains or fields.⁴⁸

The research conducted by the researcher aims to analyze the linguistic and cultural issues present in the Indonesian translation of J.R.R. Tolkien's novel "The Hobbit or There and Back Again," translated into the Indonesian language by A. Adiyoto. The inherent dissimilarities between the two languages and their respective cultures add an intriguing aspect to this study. Given the multitude of factors that can influence the outcome of a translation, this research presents an interesting opportunity for discussion and examination.

In conclusion, the given texts shed light on various aspects of translation, including linguistic and cultural challenges. Previous studies have explored the difficulties faced by translators in navigating language and cultural differences, offering valuable insights and potential solutions. The focus on the Indonesian translation of J.R.R. Tolkien's novel "The Hobbit" provides an interesting case study, highlighting the complexities of translating between languages and cultures. Overall, these studies contribute to our understanding of the intricacies involved in translation and emphasize the importance of considering linguistic and cultural factors for achieving accurate and culturally sensitive translations.

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